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Teacher-Student Relationship as Predictors of Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Prof. Nnamdi Obikeze & Ezeanowai, John Okwuchukwu

ABSTRACT

The study examined teacher-student relationship as predictors of students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 19,048 SSS2 students in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of 952 SSS 2 students (that is, 5% of the population) was used for the study. Stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was researcher-structured questionnaire titled: Teacher-Student Relationship Questionnaire (TSRQ) and Students' Academic Achievement Scores (SAAS) was used to measure students' academic achievement. The instrument was subjected to face and construct validation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method and the average coefficient of 0.81 for TSRQ was obtained and was considered reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that teacher-student communication and social interaction positively and significantly predicted students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that teacher-student relationship is effective, positive and significant predictors of students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Hence, teacher-student interactions awaken variety of developmental processes. Students who develop positive relationship with their teachers can overcome many challenges in schools. Based on the findings, the study recommended that teachers should always be up-to-date through seminars, workshops and conferences with different competencies and skills they apply in teaching in order to build an effective teacher-student relationship that would enable them perform better alongside the enhancement of students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Keywords: teacher-student relationship, students' academic achievement

INTRODUCTION

The desire to achieve something of excellence is inherent in all human beings. It is the age of competition and only good achievement pay to the students. Achieving scholastic success is a recognized individual need. Achievement refers to the ability of the individual to strive to accomplish something to do the best and to excel others in performance. Achievement is the proficiency of performance in a given skill or body of knowledge. Adinna and Anene (2024) noted that academic achievement is the outcome of general and specific learning. Academic achievement is the outcome of education, the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals.

Academic achievement is regarded as excellence in all academic disciplines, in class as well as in co-curricular activities. Enoch and Asogwa (2021) opined that the academic achievement of a child is the learning outcomes of the child, which includes the knowledge, skills, and ideas acquired and retained through their course of study within and outside the classroom situations. Okoye et al. (2021) perceived

academic achievement as students' ability in computation and problem solving, which can normally be measured by a writing test. In their view, Ezeaku and Obunike (2024) stated that academic achievement entails the achievement a student makes in school. Academic achievement deals with the extent students have gained from a particular course of instruction. Determining academic achievement helps the teacher and the students to estimate the degree of success attained in learning a given body of knowledge.

Students' academic achievement measures the amount of academic content students learn in a determined amount of time. Each grade level has learning goals or instructional standards that educators are required to teach. Standards are similar to a 'to-do' list that a teacher can use to guide instruction. When students have the support they need from their teachers, they have more freedom to focus on their academics, improving their chances of success (Adinna & Okafor, 2023). The most common kinds of problems students face are related to academics, accessibility, finances, living environment, mental health and wellness, and time management. As noted by Amaechina and Ezech (2019); Okaforcha (2024) that a student's poor achievement can be attributed to a variety of psychological factors including demotivation, discouragement, depression, hopelessness, doubtfulness and anxiety are all important psychological factors that contribute to a student's poor academic achievement in school. Enoch and Asogwa (2021) argued that the major ones were students' factors, such as students' learning skills, parental background, environmental causes, and peer influence. Similarly, teacher-related factors, school factors, socio-cultural factors, and others. Thus, Adinna and Anokwute (2023) argued that academic concerns, which might include issues such as learning difficulties or disabilities, underachievement, lack of attention from teachers and bullying, affect a number of students throughout their academic careers, from elementary school to university which result to poor academic outcome.

Contextually, the researcher defined academic performance as the amount of academic content a student learns in a specific time period. This can be any way a student has achieved short-term or long-term academic goals within an academic setting. Academic achievement is almost entirely measured with grades (by course or assignment) and Grade Point Average (GPA). Testing and assessment scores are usually performed to gauge a students' academic achievement. It is a common experience that one who fails in annual examination, is supposed to be retarded academically although he can be highly advance in the development of other aspects. However, since the understanding of concepts is a prerequisite for good academic achievement, it, therefore, requires that teacher-student relationship should not be an oversight in the teaching and learning process for the academic achievement of students in senior secondary schools.

Teacher-student relationships are the interactions between a student and teacher in a classroom with the content that is before them. A teacher-student relationship can be defined as a caring connection between a student and a teacher in the classroom (Enoch & Asogwa, 2021). Continuing, they further opined that these relationships have been shown to be a protective factor for students at-risk for failure by helping them to build resiliency and self-regulation skills. However, Umar et al. (2019); Onyekwelu and Adinna (2022) noted that the type of relationship that should exist between teachers and students should be warm and friendly so as to bring about effective transfer of learning among them and consequently students' improved academic achievement. Baafi (2021) supported teachers having qualities which will make them acceptable to the students. Baafi enumerated these qualities as including: wholesome personality characteristics; leadership qualities and democratic attitude; expressive qualities of kindness, patience, good humour, consideration and sympathy; a sense of justice and fairness in dealing with children, sensitivity to the needs of children and their reactions in different situation, professional insight into the growth pattern of children showing understanding and respect, and the ability to establish good social relationship with children.

The indices of teacher-student relationship are numerous. Umar et al. (2019) mentioned the indices of teacher-student relationship to include supervisors, classroom organisation, classroom management, leadership in the classroom, classroom interaction, discipline among others. In the words of Patiko et al. (2020), indices of teacher-student relationship are those attributes that contribute to easy teaching and learning that exists between the teachers and students in the school. They listed some of the indices to

include communication skills, social interaction, discipline and collaboration. Coristine et al. (2022) noted that indices of teacher-student relationship are the activities that bond the teachers and students in the classroom of learning which include conflict, discipline, social interaction, communication skills, feedback mechanisms, leadership, classroom activities to mention but a few.

Contextually, teacher-student relationship in the classroom is a positive relationship between the teacher and the student in efforts to gain trust and respect from each other. This relationship may consist of getting to know the students better, providing choice and encouraging the students to become stronger learners every day. By doing this, teachers are showing respect to their students, valuing their individuality and being polite. Having a positive relationship with the students help them become more successful in the classroom as well as make the classroom a safe and welcoming environment for all. In this study, two indices of teacher-student relationship was considered, they include; teacher-student communication relationship and teacher-student social interaction relationship.

Teacher-student communication relationship is the abilities of teachers to convey ideas and feelings effectively with students in the classroom settings. Ngwakwe et al. (2019) opined that good teacher-student communication relationship are the abilities and capacities that teachers use when giving and receiving different kinds of ideas, feelings or what is happening to their students in the classroom. It involves listening, speaking, observing and empathizing. Good teacher-student communication relationship encourage good communication between the teachers and the students, establish close relationship between teachers and students by holding meeting with them at intervals, building student-teacher link and impacting on the students' academic achievement in school. The importance of teacher-student communication cannot be over emphasized perhaps, that is why Obilor (2021) lamented that; possibly the most vital and fundamental element in the management process is based on working with people, which is done through some forms of communication. Nwosu (2021) also stated that keeping everyone informed is a positive way of ensuring effective leadership, co-operation, co-ordination, support and commitment by the teachers in the school for improving students' academic achievement. He believed that clear instruction on what should be done gives the students concrete direction to compliance. In this approach, teachers try to be consistent in enforcing instruction so that it produces the desired results. However, good teacher-student communication relationship in the classroom would promote improved social interaction.

A teacher who cares about their students transmits knowledge affectively and has a good interaction with them. Student-teacher social interactions are reciprocal relationships which not only influence the interacting individuals but also the quality of relationships. Omodan and Tsotetsi (2019) noted that social interaction refer to social relations of all sorts in functions, dynamic social relations of all kinds, whether such relations exist between individual and individual, between group and group and group and individual, as the case may be. Adam (2019) inferred that social interaction is the general process whereby two or more persons are in meaningful contact, as a result of which their behaviour is modified, however, slightly. The mere placing of individuals in physical proximity, although it usually results in at least a medium of interaction, does not weld them into a social unit or group. Student-teacher social interaction plays an important role in learning. Interacting with other people has proven to be quite effective in assisting the learner to organize their thoughts, reflect on their understanding, and find gaps in their reasoning. Underneath the broad umbrella of social interactions, variants can range from peer learning, reciprocal teaching, learning by teaching, learning by observation, learning by doing and self-other monitoring (Ikwele & Adinna, 2022). Underneath the broad umbrella of social interactions and learning, variants can range from peer learning, reciprocal teaching, learning by teaching, learning by observation, learning by doing, and self-other monitoring. These areas overlap in scholarship and are often an optimal way to help students learn.

Students learn in diverse ways and one of them is by bringing together experience they share with one another. For teaching and learning of students to be more effective, it demands more of interaction rather than just listening to the instruction. Hence, effective social interaction is very essential in today's act of teaching and learning. Social interaction is the relations that exist between the teacher and students in the

classroom in the course of teaching and learning (Ekperi et al., 2019). It is a practice that enhances the development of the two very important language skills which are speaking and listening among the learners. Social interaction helps the learners to be competent enough to think critically and share their views among their peers. Manafa and Adinna (2023) acknowledged that through social interaction, the learners would be able to get themselves involved with concepts, ideas and various other devices and products for language and culture learning. Good interactions in the classroom help the students to identify their own learning methods, guide them to communicate with their peers easily, give them an exposure to learning and enhance their academic achievement in school.

The issue of poor academic achievement in Mathematics among senior secondary school students in public secondary schools has been recorded in Anambra State in the recent past. Obidinnu (2022) revealed a decline in external examination achievement of students in Mathematics in Anambra State. In another study, Amaonye et al. (2022) established that there is a high repetition rate in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State which is an indicator of poor academic achievement among students. The issue of poor academic achievement is also witnessed among senior secondary students outside Nigeria. For instance, Namele et al. (2021) found poor academic achievement among senior high school students because they were not actively engaged in curricular tasks by the teachers in the school. This drastic failing standard of education in schools as reflected by the low percentage and failure of senior students in academic achievement in Mathematics is worrisome and could be linked to certain factors. Against this background, Okoye et al. (2021) noted that the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Anambra State has been linked to teacher-student relationship which entails communication patterns, classroom relationship, teachers' quality, teaching methods, classroom conflict and social interactions among others, which has resultant effects on students' academic achievement. In the face of the ugly trend in inconsistent in academic performance among senior secondary school students in Mathematics in Anambra State, there is need to determine how teacher-student relationship predict students' academic achievement in Mathematics in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. However, it is quite surprising that not much attention has been paid to teacher-student relationship in teaching and learning in Anambra State. Hence, the study deemed it necessary to examine teacher-student relationship as predictors of students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to examine teacher-student relationships as predictors of students' academic achievement in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The predictive value of teacher-student communication on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. The predictive value of social interaction on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the predictive value of teacher-student communication on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of social interaction on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. Teacher-student communication does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Social interaction does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODS

The study examined teacher-student relationship as predictors of students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 19,048 SSS2 students in 266 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of 952 SSS 2 students (that is, 5% of the population) was used for the study. Stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was researcher-structured questionnaire titled: Teacher-Student Relationship Questionnaire (TSRQ) and Students’ Academic Achievement Scores (SAAS) was used to measure students’ academic achievement. The instrument was subjected to face and construct validation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient method and the average coefficient of 0.81 for TSRQ was obtained and was considered reliable and suitable for the study. Out of 952 copies of the instrument administered, 908 (95%) of the instrument were correctly completed and returned. Simple regression analysis was used for the study.

RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the predictive value of teacher-student communication on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with teacher-student communication as it predicts academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	31.476	5.246	
Communication	0.565	0.328	0.624
R		0.624	
R ²		0.518	
Adj. R ²		0.473	

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that teacher-student communication positively predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient (R = 0.624). The coefficient of determination (R²) value of .518 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was highly strong. This implies that 52% of the variations in academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teacher-student communication. The adjusted R² supported the claim of the R² with a value of 0.473 indicating that 47% of the total variation in the dependent variable (students’ academic achievement) was explained by the independent variable (teacher-student communication). Thus, adjusted R² supports the statement that the explanatory power of teacher-student communication is highly strong in determining the academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Nevertheless, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.624$) showed that teacher-student communication is a positive predictor of academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit rise in teacher-student communication leads to 0.624(62%) increase in academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: *What is the predictive value of social interaction on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with teacher-student social interaction as it predicts academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β
Constant	29.348	5.875	
Social Interaction	0.582	0.439	0.627
R	0.627		
R ²	0.541		
Adj. R ²	0.462		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 indicated that teacher-student social interaction positively predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.627$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.541 showed that the explanatory power of the variable was highly strong. This implies that 54% of the variations in academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teacher-student social interaction. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.462 indicating that 46% of the total variation in the dependent variable (students' academic achievement) was explained by the independent variable (teacher-student social interaction). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teacher-student social interaction is highly strong in determining the academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.627$) showed that teacher-student social interaction is a positive predictor of academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit improvement in social interaction leads to 0.627(63%) increase in academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

H₀₁: Teacher-student communication does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with teacher-student communication as it predicts academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	31.476	5.246		23.841	0.000
Communication	0.565	0.328	0.624	27.683	0.000
R	0.624				
R ²	0.518				
Adj. R ²	0.473				
F	41.125				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 revealed that the regression coefficient (R) is 0.624 while the R^2 is 0.518 and Adjust R^2 is 0.473. The F-ratio associated with regression is 41.125, the t-test is 27.683 and the p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that teacher-student communication does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that

teacher-student communication significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2

H₀₂: Social interaction does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with teacher-student social interaction as it predicts academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-	p-
	β	β	β	value	value
Constant	29.348	5.875		21.532	0.000
Social Interaction	0.582	0.439	0.627	28.486	0.000
R	0.627				
R ²	0.541				
Adj. R ²	0.462				
F	38.327				0.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 revealed that the regression coefficient (R) is 0.627 while the R² is 0.541 and Adjust R² is 0.462. The F-ratio associated with regression is 38.327, the t-test is 28.486 and the p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that teacher-student social interaction does not significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that teacher-student social interaction significantly predict academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Findings on the predictive value of teacher-student communication on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that teacher-student communication positively predicted academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also showed that teacher-student communication significantly predicted academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is as a result of the respondents accepting the fact that teachers: exchange ideas with their students in classroom learning; engage in dialogue with students to upgrade their knowledge; use to have classroom discussion with students on interval basis; create meaningful dialogue among students; provide enough information to student to complete classroom assignment; involve students in active classroom communication to improve their socials skills; always interact with students at the end of each lesson to improves their level of understanding of course; always listen to students’ questions; discuss academic issues with students on a regular basis; and practice face to face communication in the classroom teaching. This is supported by the findings of Amadi and Akpan (2018) that children who have been described as actively engaged in classroom activities have been found to have more positive academic outcomes. It also supports the conclusion by Omodan and Tsotetsi (2019), that secondary schools are the application of pedagogical knowledge into a classroom-oriented plan of action which constitute the most essential fabric upon which the success of the school, its administration and the entire democratic process rest. This showed that students’ communication and engagement with their teachers will help them learn how to navigate the environment of the classroom (Ngwakwe et al., 2019). This is also in line with attachment theory that could be used to better understand how children develop positive working relationships with their teachers. In the words of Obilor (2021), teachers’ communication skills of speaking, listening, attitude, gestures and facial expression have impact on students’ academic performance. The similarities found among these studies could be attributed to the fact that teacher-

student communication relationship would help students to be more interactive in classrooms if they have strong communication with their teachers. This interaction will lead to better clarity in understanding the subjects being taught. This would, in turn, lead to much better grades and eventual success in academics. Findings on the predictive value of teacher-student social interaction on academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that teacher-student social interaction positively predicted academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study also showed that teacher-student social interaction significantly predicted academic achievement of SS2 students in Mathematics in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is as a result of the respondents accepting the fact that classroom interaction makes the classroom learning to be fun, helps students to know how to work together with others, makes students want to come to class regularly, helps students develop social skills, improves students' communication skills, promotes self-assigned roles in groups, helps students learn from others, makes students to actively participate more in classroom activities, helps students become confident in themselves, and helps students to produce more ideas. The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Adam (2019) who asserted that classroom social interactions are essential aspects of social relationships that positively impact on students' academic success. This is in consonance with the findings of Enoch and Asogwa (2021) that classroom social interactions among students positively and significantly contribute to students' high academic achievement in schools. Cooperation, accommodation, conflict and social exchange among students in classroom are components of social interaction according to Nguyen (2021) that significantly impact on academic success of students. The similarities among the studies are as a result of the impact of positive classroom social interactions towards academic achievement of students.

CONCLUSION

Teacher-student relationship has been in existence since time immemorial. Across the globe, teachers are expected to relate with their students positively. Teachers create lifelong learners and learners' goal cannot be achieved if there is enmity between teachers and students. The study therefore concluded that teacher-student relationship is positive and significant predictor on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should always be up-to-date through seminars, workshops and conferences with different competencies and skills they apply in teaching in order to build an effective teacher-student relationship that would enable them perform better alongside the enhancement of students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Intensive efforts should be made by all relevant stakeholders to work towards improving the existing relationships between students and teachers. This should be done vis-à-vis other subordinate staff that works directly or indirectly in the schools to better the current students' academic achievement through professional inspection of teachers and other supervisory actions for effective teaching and learning.

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